

Requests (1–2) for a binding decision on the name-giving taxa in the names *Isoeto-Cicendietum* Br.-Bl. 1967 and *Verbena-Gnaphalietum* Rivas Goday 1970

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Abstract

We propose to complete two association names of the class *Isoeto-Nanojuncetea* by selecting the name-giving taxa according to Art. 40 of the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature.

Taxonomic reference: Euro+Med (2021).

Keywords

binding decision, *Isoeto-Nanojuncetea*, nomenclature, phytosociology

(1) Request for a binding decision on the name-giving taxon in the name *Isoeto longissimae-Cicendietum* Br.-Bl. 1967 nom. corr.

Original form of the name: *Isoeto-Cicendietum*

Syn.: *Isoeto velatae-Cicendietum* Br.-Bl. 1967 nom. in-
ept. (Art. 44)

Typus: Braun-Blanquet 1967: 29 (holotypus).

Braun-Blanquet (1967: 29) published this Galician-Portuguese syntaxon with only one relevé from Braga (Minho province, Portugal), which is therefore

the holotype. The only *Isoetes* in the original diagnosis is *Isoetes velata* A. Braun. However, as this is an illegitimate name (Troia and Greuter 2014), the correct name of the name-giving taxon of the association is *Isoetes longissima* Bory, and the name of the syntaxon must be corrected (Art. 44, Theurillat et al. 2021).

Braun-Blanquet did not indicate from which of the two *Cicendia* species present in the original diagnosis the association name was formed, *C. filiformis* or *C. pusilla* (= *Exaculum pusillum*; Euro+Med 2021). However, *C. filiformis* is more abundant in the type relevé (cover-abundance value 1) than *C. pusilla* (value +). As far as we can ascertain, no other relevés assigned to this association have been published (see, e.g., Brullo and Minissale 1998). Thus, we propose to select *Cicendia filiformis* as the name-giving taxon.

(2) Request for a binding decision on the name-giving taxon in the name *Gnaphalio-Verbenetum supinae* Rivas Goday 1970 nom. invers.

Original form of the name: *Verbena-Gnaphalietum*

Syn.: “com. prov. *Gnaphalium luteo-album-Verbena supina*” Rivas Goday 1956 (Art. 3b, 3c)

Typus: Rivas Goday 1970: 270–271, table 8, rel. 1 (lectotypus designated by Silva et al. 2021: 8).

The provisional community “*Gnaphalium luteo-album-Verbena supina*” was published by Rivas Goday in Rivas Goday et al. (1956: 370) together with seven relevés. Later, Rivas Goday (1970: 273) validated the syntaxon under the name “*Verbena-Gnaphalietum* Rivas Goday 1955”, giving an unambiguous reference to his older work (though with the wrong year 1955; see Izco (1975) for information about the correct publication date) and publishing another table with ten relevés. The only *Verbena* species in the original diagnosis is *V. supina*, but there are two species of *Gnaphalium*: *G. luteoalbum* and *G. uliginosum*. Rivas Goday et al. (1956) used *G. luteoalbum* in the name of their provisional community, and this species

is also more frequent and abundant in the original diagnosis than *G. uliginosum*. We therefore propose to select *G. luteoalbum* as the name-giving taxon of the *Verbena-Gnaphalietum*.

In the type relevé, *Verbena supina* has a cover-abundance value of 2, whereas *G. luteoalbum* has a 1 and *G. uliginosum* a +. Therefore, the name ‘*Verbena-Gnaphalietum*’ must be inverted (Arts. 10b and 42, Theurillat et al. 2021). If our proposal is accepted, the correct name of the association will be ‘*Gnaphalio luteoalbi-Verbenetum supinae* Rivas Goday 1970 nom. invers.’.

Author contributions

Both authors have contributed to the nomenclature research and writing the manuscript.

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